

Multiple parallel twinning overgrowth in nanostructured dense cobalt ferrite

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Abstract

Cobalt ferrite powders were synthesized by solid state reaction of the nanosized starting oxides at different temperatures. The highly aggregated powders were milled, and the aggregate size was reduced from 25 – 40 μm to 12 – 20 μm , depending on the milling time. A correlation between milling media diameter and final granulometry, and an unexpected calcination temperature effect on the milling efficiency were found. Highly homogenous green bodies and fully dense materials were produced for the first time after conventional sintering. The crystallite size depends primarily on the heating conditions and decreases from 50 – 70 nm to 27 – 13 nm. Under the same sintering conditions, particle morphology and crystallite size control the final grain shape, producing twinned grains with increased multiple parallel twinning overgrowth for the finer starting dimensions. The sintered cobalt ferrite ceramics show a relative density of 96 - 99 %. The higher the planar faults density and grain size, the lower is the induced magnetization due to increased domain walls pinning. The variation of initial susceptibility was explained by extending the Globus model to the case where the domain walls are pinned at twinning boundaries. A linear correlation between multiparallel-twinned grains fraction and initial susceptibility was found.

Keywords: spinel ferrite, planetary milling, particle size distribution, sintering, initial susceptibility, Globus model.

Introduction

Cobalt ferrite, CoFe_2O_4 , is a well-known magnetic material applied in several technological fields including high-density magnetic recording media [1], sensors [2], spintronics [3], telecommunications [4], biomedical, and biological applications [5]. Nowadays, a renewed interest is shown in cobalt ferrite because of its interesting properties, such as strong magnetocrystalline anisotropy - and hence high coercivity - large magnetostriction, moderate saturation magnetization, good mechanical hardness, chemical stability [6], and the possibility of employing it in magnetoelectric and photomagnetic materials [7,8] and metamaterials [9]. The properties of CoFe_2O_4 depend strongly on crystallite size, grain shape, purity and cations distribution via exchange interaction between tetrahedral and octahedral site cations, which in turn depend on sample preparation method. Several innovative methods have been investigated in order to enhance or tailor CoFe_2O_4 properties, including sonochemical reactions [10], mechanochemical synthesis [11], hydrothermal hydrolysis [12], sol-gel auto-combustion [13]. The traditional solid-state method still offers the advantage of higher reproducibility, large scale production and lower cost, but it must include additional steps to improve the final microstructure by reducing the crystallite size towards the nanometric range. When starting with nanosized raw materials, their high reactivity results in agglomerated particles, and milling produces homogenous final microstructures. Critical to phases homogeneity are the synthesis method of the starting powder and the resulting powder morphology. In this work, the production process of cobalt ferrite from nanosized starting powders is investigated in order to produce dense bodies and engineer grain growth by introducing mechanically induced lattice defects in the powders. In fact, an exaggerated growth of the spinel structures can be triggered or avoided – during microstructure evolution – by controlling the creation of planar defects, such as twinning, inversion and antiphase boundary [14]. Homogeneous, controlled and narrow distribution of the nanocrystallites can only be achieved by careful milling after solid-state reaction of the starting oxides. Several papers deal with the study of the effect of the calcination temperature on properties of synthesized cobalt ferrite powders [15, 16], but only few of them consider the influence of calcination temperature and milling on microstructure development and densification of sintered bulk cobalt ferrite. Intensive investigation of partial substitution in tetrahedral and/or octahedral cobalt ferrite sites was performed [17, 18], more focus being placed in later works on the microstructural features of bulk cobalt ferrite [19, 20]. We focused on the sintered materials: the main objectives was to study the effect of both calcination temperature and milling on particle size distribution (PSD) and crystallite size D_x (down to the nanoscale) on densification, and to what extent

PSD and D_x influence grain growth during sintering. In addition to optimizing the solid-state process, as confirmed by the full densification achieved, we also investigated the effect of the different microstructures on the magnetic properties of the sintered cobalt ferrite bodies.

Method

Cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4 , CFO in the following) powders were synthesized by solid state reaction of nanosized cobalt oxide powder (Co_3O_4 , Aldrich 637025), and nanosized iron oxide (Fe_2O_3 , Aldrich 544884). The powders were mixed with ethanol in a polyethylene bottle at room temperature, and milled for 24 h with zirconia balls. The powders were then dried and heat-treated at different temperatures and soaking times. In this study, the following calcination conditions were employed: 700 °C for 4 h, 800 °C for 4 h, 850 °C for 2 h, and 1000 °C for 4 h. The heat-treated powders were further wet-milled in ethanol at room temperature by planetary milling (PM) at 400 rpm in a stainless steel jar filled to 75 vol.%, with a constant grinding balls/powders mass ratio of 4.5. The powders heat-treated at 850 °C and 1000 °C were milled in 75 steps (with pauses of 5 min between steps) using zirconia balls of 1 mm diameter during the whole process. In order to investigate the influence of the size of the milling media, the powder calcined at 800 °C was milled in 60 steps (as above) gradually decreasing the zirconia balls size every 15 steps, from 5 mm, to 3 mm, 2 mm, and 1 mm. The milled powders were then cold-consolidated into discs of 30 mm diameter by die pressing at 50 MPa, followed by cold isostatic pressing at 250 MPa. The samples were sintered at 1200 °C for 2 h.

The Particle Size Distribution (PSD) of the as-calcined and post-milled CFO powders was determined as equivalent spherical diameter, d , based on settling velocity ('velocity of the Equivalent Spherical Diameter, ESD') [21] using a Micromeritics SediGraph 5100 apparatus [22]. The sample was prepared by diluting 1.50 g of CFO powder in 75 ml of 0.1 mol/l Calgon dispersing solution, resulting in a sample concentration of 20 g l⁻¹ (≈ 0.4 vol.%), and then sonicated for 1 min immediately before analysis. The sample was analysed at the highest possible resolution, yielding a total of 104 data points (cumulative mass percentage finer). Data acquisition and processing were performed using standard Micromeritics software, and the density distribution was calculated as the derivative of the measured cumulative mass percentage finer with respect to the velocity ESD (particles size), approximated using finite intervals [23].

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) patterns of the powders were obtained at room temperature on a Bruker D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer (θ - θ) using Cu K_{α} radiation in the $15^{\circ} \leq 2\theta \leq 70^{\circ}$ range, at 2.4°/min scanning rate. The average crystallite size d of the calcined and milled powders was calculated from XRD data, using Scherrer's formula ($d = 0.9 \lambda / (\beta \cos \theta)$), where $\lambda = 0.15418$ nm is the wavelength of X-ray, θ is the Bragg's diffraction angle, and β is the true half-peak width of the X-ray diffraction lines [24]). The morphology and particle size distribution of the powders and the microstructure of the sintered samples were investigated by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis of as-sintered and fracture surfaces, performed on a ZEISS SIGMA Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy system (FE-SEM) (SEM operating voltages (ETH) and working distance (WD) are shown in each secondary electron (SE) micrograph). Grains population was calculated by means of analysis of the SE images using the Image-Pro Analyzer 7.0 software to measure the area covered by each grain. The relative density of the sintered samples was calculated as the ratio of their density, determined by the Archimedes' method, to the theoretical density of cobalt ferrite (5.304 g cm^{-3}). The induced magnetization (M) of the sintered samples was measured using a YSZ 02C Sartorius susceptometer, collecting seven points at each of five different distances from the permanent magnet, and its two orientations [25]. The corresponding field-independent susceptibility, called initial susceptibility (χ_i), was calculated by fitting the experimental induced magnetization values to the Rayleigh law ($M = \chi_i H + \alpha H^2$; where α is the Rayleigh coefficient [26, 27]).

Results

Fig. 1 shows the morphology of the starting Co_3O_4 and Fe_2O_3 nano-powders. Both powders were found to be nanosized, with particles smaller than 50 nm, with Co_3O_4 displaying a narrower particles size distribution and a lower mean particle size than Fe_2O_3 .

Fig. 1 SEM images of the starting nano-powders a) Co_3O_4 and b) $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$. (two- column)

Iron oxide with cubic structure, which can be indexed to maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, ICDD-PDF No. 25-1402, \wedge symbol), and spinel cobalt oxide (ICDD-PDF No. 42-1467, * symbol) were the phases present in the starting mixture (Fig. 2). The thermal treatments promote the maghemite-to-hematite transformation and cobalt ferrite formation. At 700 °C the maghemite is fully transformed into hematite ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, ICDD-PDF No. 33-0664, + symbol), and the formation of the spinel cobalt ferrite (ICDD-PDF No. 22-1086, \circ symbol) is evidenced by the shift towards the right of the peaks of the cubic phase (Fig. 2). The amount of unreacted precursors decreased with increasing calcination temperature, and pure cobalt ferrite powder was obtained after calcination at 850 °C for 2 h (Fig. 2). By evaluating the reaction yield as $I_{\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4} (3\ 1\ 1) / [I_{\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4} (3\ 1\ 1) + I_{\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3} (1\ 0\ 4)]$ (which can be considered a good approximation since the mass absorption of the two phases is only slightly different), the value increases from 80 % to 91% and 100 % with increasing calcination temperature, from 700 °C to 800 °C and 850 °C, respectively (note that at 850 °C 2h soaking time is sufficient to cause full transformation of the starting oxides). Calculations based on peak broadening (inset in Fig. 2) show that the CFO crystallite size increases from 48.8 nm at 700 °C to 75.5 nm at 800°C. The powder calcined at 850 °C shows an average crystallite size of 70.3 nm, due to the reduction of the soaking time, even though the temperature was 50 °C higher. Owing to the high amount of unreacted starting oxides, the powder treated at 700 °C will not be further considered. Besides small crystallite size, the synthesis of cobalt ferrite from nanopowders produces coarse, partially sintered, and slow-reacting powders already upon reaction at 800 °C, with agglomerate size as large as 60 - 80 μm , which caused a milling step to be

required prior to cold consolidation. The PSD analyses of the milled powders are shown in Fig. 3 and compared with the as-reacted powders. The XRD spectra of the milled powders shown in Fig. 4 show that milling causes the decrease of the average crystallite size from 26.8 nm to 20.4 nm for the powders calcined at 800 °C, and 850 °C, respectively. Milling decreased the crystallite size of the powder calcined at 1000°C for 4 h to 13 nm (under the same milling conditions of the powder calcined at 850°C).

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of the starting oxides reacted at 700 °C, 800 °C and 850 °C, before milling. In the inset the (3 1 1) peak at half height is enlarged for the three samples (1,5 - column)

Fig. 3 Comparison of Sedigraph analyses of the as-calcined and milled powders. (1.5- column)

Fig. 4 XRD patterns of the reacted powders after planetary milling. Cobalt ferrite peaks are labeled with the respective Miller indices. In the inset the (3 1 1) peak at half height is enlarged for the three samples (1.5- column)

SEM micrographs of the milled powders (Fig. 5) confirm that the powders calcined at 1000 °C are finer than those calcined at 850 °C, and are characterized by a greater amount of primary particles having size around 10 nm. The average primary particle size is smaller than 200 nm for all the milled powders.

Fig. 5 SEM morphology of the milled powders calcined at a) 850 °C and b) 1000 °C. (2- column)

The same trend was found with the analysis by sedimentation (Fig. 3) even though the density distributions (q) – calculated as the derivative of the measured cumulative mass percentage finer (Q) with respect to the velocity ESD (particle size) and approximated using finite intervals – yielded values of the order of tens of microns. These higher values, compared to the SEM morphology and particle size, are due to agglomeration during drying. Considering that agglomeration occurs in all the samples, it is worth analysing in more depth the milling efficiency. In Fig. 6 the mean particle size (which takes into account the agglomerated population [28]) is shown as a function of the milling time for the powders calcined at 800 °C, 850 °C and 1000 °C. The particle size, weighted on the equivalent spherical diameter (d_{nl}) and on the volume (d_{nV}), was calculated as $\sum q_i \cdot d_i / \sum q_i$ and $(\sum q_i \cdot (d_i)^3 / \sum q_i)^{1/3}$, where q is the density distribution value of the particles having diameter d [28]. In a non-normal distribution, the d_{nl} value is smaller than the d_{nV} , which attributes greater weight to bigger particles (volume is proportional to the cube of the diameter). Therefore in Fig. 6 the slope of the d_{nl} (dotted lines) and d_{nV} (straight lines) curves allows the separation of the effect of milling on the finer and coarser particles. In fact, from the ratio $R = (\Delta d_{nV} / \Delta t) / (\Delta d_{nl} / \Delta t)$ it is possible to determine whether the particle size

distribution becomes narrower or wider with the milling time (t). If the value of R is higher than 1, then the distribution is narrower, the opposite if R is lower than 1.

Fig. 6 Influence of milling time on the mean particle size distribution (PSD). Labels refer to the diameter of milling media. (1.5- column)

The results of the milling tests performed on the CFO calcined powders are reported in Tab.1. For the powder calcined at 800 °C and milled in four subsequent steps (the milling media were replaced with smaller ones, from 5 mm to 3 mm, 2 mm and 1 mm, as detailed in Fig. 6), it was found that the above mentioned ratio was higher than 1 for all the steps, but the highest efficiency was found for the milling with ball size of 5 mm ($R= 2.3$) and 1 mm ($R= 1.6$).

Tab. 1- Results of the milling process performed on the CFO powders calcined at 800 °C, 850°C and 1000°C

Milling time (t)	CFO800			CFO850			CFO1000		
	d _{nl}	d _{nv}	R	d _{nl}	d _{nv}	R	d _{nl}	d _{nv}	R
h	μm			μm			μm		
0	25.4	35.5		28.7	38.4		29.4	34.7	
5	22.4	28.6	2.3	-	-		-	-	
10	18.8	23.9	1.3	-	-		-	-	
15	17.5	22.0	1.5	-	-		-	-	
20	14.8	17.7	1.6	-	-		-	-	
25	-	-	-	12.7	18.2	1.3	11.0	16.1	1.0

$$R = (\Delta d_{nv} / \Delta t) / (\Delta d_{nl} / \Delta t)$$

Moreover, for the investigated milling time, the particle size decrease is far from being asymptotic towards the lower limit. As the milling time increases, the particle size distribution always tends to become narrower, and the mean size (d_{nl} and d_{nv}) tends to decrease.

From the above considerations on the Sedigraph data, the main results are: 1) the highest milling efficiency was achieved with the powder calcined at 1000 °C; 2) the highest PSD reduction was achieved by starting with grinding media size about 25 times larger than the powder to be milled and changing the grinding media throughout as explained. In Fig. 7 the relative density of the green and sintered samples is plotted vs. starting particle size (expressed as D₅₀).

All the sintered samples were pure cobalt ferrite, (as shown by the XRD analysis not shown here) and the highest density resulted from the compromise between high green density (arising from the high particle packing resulting from the milling treatment) and high reactivity of the powders, that increases with the calcination temperature as discussed above. In fact, by sintering at 1200 °C for 2 h, fully dense cobalt ferrite (99.1 %) was achieved when setting the calcination temperature at 850 °C for 2 h, and milling for 25 h with zirconia balls of 1 mm size.

Fig. 7 Density of the cold-consolidated and sintered samples as a function of the mean particle size (D_{50}) of the starting powders. (*single column*)

The microstructure of the sintered materials is shown in Fig. 8. The surface structure of the CFO samples which were sintered together (i.e. exactly in the same conditions) reveals that the lower is the calcination temperature, the more homogeneous and finer is the microstructure (Fig. 8 a) c) e)). At higher magnification (Fig. 8 b) d) f)) it can be seen that the sample calcined at 800 °C (Fig. 8 b)) is composed of sparse grains having simple isometric octahedral morphology. Some grains are twinned, but most grains are overgrown. The faces of the larger grains are marked by outcropped striae parallel to the $\{111\}$ planes. Such morphology shows that twinned grains are arranged in thin triangular lamellae lying onto the $\{111\}$ octahedral planes, in agreement with the spinel law. This characteristic in-plane arrangement of twinned crystals is known as the sagenite network [29]. This type of overgrowth twinning seems to suggest that the twinned boundaries nucleate continuously on any of the available $\{111\}$ surface of spinel crystals during crystal growth, forming complex twin combinations [14]. In Fig. 8 d) it can be seen that, for the grains in the centre and in the lower left corner, the twin boundaries are nucleated on each of the $\{111\}$ planes, giving a multiple cyclic twinning. Then, the growth continues through multiple parallel twinning, as is proved by the right angles between twin boundaries laying on two adjacent $\{111\}$ planes. One can speculate that, as a consequence of this growing mode, a seed grain gets covered with thin platelet crystal domains on the sides of the twin boundaries. The width of the twin lamellae is about 200 nm as is shown in Fig. 9. The microstructure

becomes even more complex as a consequence of the nucleation of new crystals that can take place in the interstices between two platelet crystal domains. In fact, small grains with simple isometric octahedral morphology or twinned on the top of such overgrown crystals (Fig. 8 d) and Fig. 9)) can be seen. In any case, twinned domains grow almost exclusively parallel to the twinning plane, displaying a rapid anisotropic growth and developing a plate-like morphology.

Fig. 8 SEM morphology of the as-sintered surfaces: (a,b) CFO 800 °C; (c,d) CFO 850 °C and (e, f) CFO 1000 °C. (2- column)

Fig. 9 SEM morphology of twin lamellae (sample CFO 850 °C). (*single column*)

The multiple parallel twinning, maybe occurring on every face of the primary octahedral crystal of the spinel structure, predominates in the CFO 1000 °C sample, which displays extremely thin tabular crystals for which no simple isometric octahedral morphology or twinned grains were observed (Fig 8 e) and f)). As the reactivity of the powder increases, the grain size increases as well but the sintered samples were found to consist of highly defective structures, such as twin boundaries. Therefore, the sintered sample from the powder calcined at 1000°C displays the more pronounced grain growth in the out-of-plane $\langle 111 \rangle$ directions, and finer stacking sequence during sintering, thus resulting in a fully plate-like abnormal polycrystalline microstructure (Fig. 8 e) f)). This strongly anisotropic growth introduces a high internal crystal anisotropy within the spinel structure. Such microstructure gives a conchoidal macroscopic fracture. The fracture process causes the fracture surface to develop in a transgranular fashion, but, as can be seen at high magnification (Fig. 10), it is affected by the presence of parting planes (the small outcropped fissures).

Fig. 10 SEM morphology of the fracture surface of the CFO sample sintered at 1000 °C. (*1.5 column*)

From a functional point of view, the increase of multiparallel-twinning grains overgrowth is reflected on the magnetic susceptibility as is shown by the magnetization curves (Fig. 11), which provide evidence of a significant difference in magnetization. Taking into account that the CFO 800 °C, CFO 850 °C, and CFO 1000 °C samples have 0.830, 0.958, and 0.997 multiparallel-twinning grains volume-fraction (G_{MPT}), respectively, it is clear that the induced magnetization decreases as G_{MPT} increases (Fig. 11). As expected for a ferromagnetic material, the linear relationship $M = \chi_i H$ is not satisfied for magnetic fields higher than 10 A m^{-1} [27, 29], but it was observed that the data follow the Rayleigh law up to 2700 A m^{-1} (solid lines in Fig. 11). The fitted values of the Rayleigh parameters are shown in Fig. 11 together with those of adjusted R^2 . In this way, it is possible to observe that the sample with the highest G_{MPT} (0.997) displays the lowest initial susceptibility (0.3) and a weak contribution of the field-dependent term of susceptibility (αH , $\alpha = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m A}^{-1}$) is shown. A remarkable increase of both χ_i and α , up to 0.9 and $9.2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m A}^{-1}$ respectively, was achieved by reducing G_{MPT} down to 0.83 . In order to gain an idea of the effect of G_{MPT} , χ_i , and αH contribution on the measured susceptibility according to the field intensity, Fig. 12 was constructed showing the total volume susceptibility ($\chi = \chi_i + \alpha H$) vs. field intensity (H) and the volume fraction of multiparallel-twinning grains (G_{MPT}). It can be seen in Fig. 12 that there is a linear correlation (adjusted $R^2 = 1$) between χ_i and G_{MPT} (the black line at $H = 0$ on the G_{MPT} - χ_i plane). In particular, χ_i decreases as G_{MPT} increases. The contribution αH on the measured susceptibility is negligible, $\chi_i \approx \chi$, at $G_{MPT} = 0.997$ (the gray line almost parallel to the G_{MPT} - H planes, and perpendicular to the G_{MPT} - χ_i planes), but it increases with decreasing G_{MPT} as can be seen from the increase of the slope projected by the gray curves on the H - χ_i plane. In particular the ratio of the αH term to the χ at the field intensity of 2700 A m^{-1} ($\alpha H / \chi_{2700}$) is 0.01 , 0.15 , and 0.22 when G_{MPT} is equal to 0.997 , 0.958 , and 0.83 , respectively.

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Fig. 11 Induced magnetization of the sintered samples vs. magnetic field strength. Magnetic field strength increases as a result of the samples being brought closer to the permanent magnet at five set distances. The solid lines follow the Rayleigh law parameterized by initial susceptibility (χ_i), and Rayleigh coefficient (α) [26]. (single column)

Fig. 12 Plot of volume magnetic susceptibility ($\chi = \chi_i + \alpha H$) as a function of magnetic field strength (H), and multiparallel-twinned grains volume fraction (G_{MPT}). (1.5 column)

Discussion

In comparison to starting micrometer-sized powders, nanosized oxides should allow a significant reduction of soaking time for the synthesis of pure cobalt ferrite by solid-state reaction. According to the phase diagram, in ambient atmosphere pure CoFe_2O_4 with cubic spinel structure can be stabilized from 740.5°C , while at 700°C it is at equilibrium with a 0.46 wt.% amount of hematite [31] which cannot be detected by XRD analysis due to its small mass fraction. The reaction yields, calculated from XRD spectra, confirm an amount of hematite phase higher than 3 wt.% (the reference intensity ratio (RIR) method of quantitative phase analysis gives results accurate to within $\sim\pm 3$ wt.% at the 95% confidence level [32]). This applies also to the stoichiometric mixture of nano-powders calcined for 4 h at about 60°C over the theoretical equilibrium temperature. Being based on a solid state reaction, the relatively high hematite amount depends on temperature/time controlled diffusion and reaction distance, i.e. particle size. In fact, in this work, the amount of hematite after calcination of the nanopowders at

700 °C is higher than that obtained, for example, using powder synthesized by the sol-gel method heated at the same temperature but with shorter soaking time [33, 34]. Mixed nanosized oxides allow the synthesis of pure cobalt ferrite by solid-state reaction at 850 °C for 2 h, and an almost full-density final microstructure is achieved after sintering at 1200 °C for 2 h. Furthermore, besides equilibrium issues, the solid state reaction at the above mentioned temperatures results into hard agglomerates and partially sintered particles that require a properly designed milling step before cold consolidation and sintering. After calcination at 700 – 1000 °C the particles are strongly agglomerated, with different broadening of the PSD depending on the calcination temperature (Fig. 3, dashed lines), the primary particles size ranges from 10 nm to about 200 nm and the crystallite size is tens of nanometers. Conventional planetary milling proved to be quite efficient in reducing crystallite, particle, and agglomerate size. Size reduction displayed a quite unexpected trend, as both the crystallite size and the agglomerate size resulted smaller for the powder treated at 1000 °C for 4 h (Fig. 3 solid lines, and Fig. 4). This means that the crystallite's size and the absorbed energy are inversely correlated to the calcination temperature. This could be due to higher probability of critical defects, as well as to the higher stresses concentrated into the larger particles during the milling treatment, causing particles to be fractured into smaller pieces. Therefore, the powders calcined at higher temperature may be less tough due to higher crystallite size (Fig. 2) and agglomerate size (Fig. 3, dashed lines) so that they are crushed more easily (Fig. 6) or can absorb energy by a decrease of the crystallinity (Fig. 4). Taking into account the Hertz theory for the contact of elastic bodies, and the assumption that only flaws at the location of the highest tensile stress are activated and induce the particle breakage according to the Weibull statistics, it was demonstrated that the breakage rates are exponentially correlated to the particle diameter, and depend on the minimum energy which can be stored in the particle without breakage [35, 36]. Reducing primary particle size and crystallite size enhances the driving force for densification. In fact, the grain coarsening (Fig. 8) achieved by the CFO powders calcined at 1000 °C for 4 h and then milled is greater than for the two powders characterized by starting larger particle/crystallite size (solid lines in Fig. 3, and inset in Fig. 4). During sintering the powders crystallize with the same structure, but they grow with different morphologies, with a homogeneous overall microstructure. However, due to the above tailored milling treatments, the achieved densification is higher than, for example, after intensive two-step thermal treatment up to 1500 °C [37]. It should be emphasized that the multiple parallel twinning growth of cubic spinel crystals is an interesting phenomenon worthy of further investigation in view of the joint enhancement of strength and toughness. In fact, it is well known that one of the methods for toughening ceramics is the addition

of plate-like particles in order to dissipate energy by toughening mechanisms like cracks blunting, cracks deflecting, and daughter crack formation [38].

The magnetic measurements suggest that all the sintered samples can be regarded as hard magnetic materials, due to their low initial magnetic susceptibility [39]. It is important to remark that the initial susceptibility ($\chi_i = 0.3 - 0.9$) is very low in comparison to that of other soft ferrites like Zn-Mn ferrites ($\chi_i \approx 1000$) or Ni-Zn ferrite ($\chi_i \approx 650$). On the other hand, the relative differences among them are remarkably high: a 67 % reduction of the effective volume susceptibility was achieved by enhancing the multiple parallel twinning overgrowth in accordance with work by Yan et al. [40]. The variation of χ_i can be explained on the basis of Globus model where domain walls are pinned at grain boundaries and reversible wall motion is caused by wall bulging under application of a magnetic field until a critical value is reached at which the wall gets unpinned [29, 41, 42]. In this model the linear correlation between the initial susceptibility and the mean grain diameter is expressed as: $\chi_i = 2\pi M_s^2 D_m / K$, where M_s is the saturation magnetization, K is the global anisotropy, composed of the magnetocrystalline anisotropy and the magnetoelastic anisotropy, and D_m is the mean grain size. According to this model χ_i is proportional to the average grain diameter (D_m). But in our case, such model has to be extended to the case where the domain walls are pinned at twinning boundaries and D_m can be interpreted as the distance between the twinning boundaries, i.e. the span of the domain wall. Since, in spite of the fact that the grain size increases with increasing calcination temperature, the initial susceptibility decreases owing to multiple parallel twinning overgrowth. From the experimental linear correlation between χ_i and G_{MPT} (Fig.12), it is possible to calculate the different contribution of multiple-twinned grains on the total initial susceptibility (χ_i') using the mixing rule: $\chi_i' = a G_{MPT} + b (1 - G_{MPT})$, where a and b are constants whose values are 0.3 and 3.9 respectively. When $G_{MPT} = 1$, $\chi_i' = 0.3$, which gives the total initial susceptibility of a sample in which all grains are grown by multiple parallel twinning, while for $G_{MPT} = 0$ there are not multiparallel-twinned grains and $\chi_i' = 3.9$. Therefore, in order to apply the Globus model to the macroscopic magnetization of a spinel ferrite, it is not enough to simply measure the sample's grain size, but consideration is required of the contribution of multiple parallel twinning to the physical parameter D_m [29]. As for the initial susceptibility, the different contribution of multiple-twinned grains on the Rayleigh coefficient was extrapolated by using the mixing rule: $\alpha = c G_{MPT} + d (1 - G_{MPT})$. The calculated values of c and d are $1.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ A}^{-1} \text{ m}$ and $5.3 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ A}^{-1} \text{ m}$, respectively. This means that the multiparallel-twinned grains are less susceptible to the

applied magnetic field (nanopowders feature enhanced hard magnetic behaviour [42, 43]) while the other grains (having not so high a density of twin boundaries in the volume of the grain) display higher susceptibility. Moreover, these results suggest the possibility of producing bulk cobalt ferrite characterized by a nano-sagenite network where the distance between the twin boundaries is comparable to, or lower than, a single domain (about 200 times the size of the unit cells [44]). The possibility of tuning the magnetic behaviour from a multidomain to a single domain scale allows bulk cobalt ferrite to be competitive with its nanoparticles, while keeping the advantages of bulk ceramics. This powerful feature substantially increases the versatility of spinel ferrites in their applications, because the production and manipulation issues related to nanoparticles are completely avoided, and may offer unprecedented opportunities in the integration of nanostructures bulk spinel ferrites with applications in electronics, spintronic devices, data storage and silicon-based technologies.

Conclusions

Calcination and milling protocols of cobalt ferrite powders were optimized in view of obtaining enhanced density and microstructure homogeneity in the sintered state. Pure cobalt ferrite was obtained after calcination of the starting oxides at 850 °C for 2 h. A relationship between calcination temperature and milling efficiency was found. The milling efficiency was improved starting with zirconia balls 25 times larger than the average particle size (weighted average on volume). Fully dense (up to 99.1 %) CFO ceramic was obtained starting from pure cobalt ferrite powders milled for 25 h by planetary milling. Induced magnetization data measured by susceptometry follow the Rayleigh law, and show an increase of hard magnetic behaviour of the cobalt ferrite with increasing overgrowth of the multiparallel-twinned grains. The completely nanostructured dense cobalt ferrite displays an initial susceptibility of 0.3 and a negligible field-dependent susceptibility term up to 2700 A m⁻¹. The decrease of the initial susceptibility with increasing grain size, combined with the reduction of the distance between twinned lamellae, suggests an application of the Globus model in considering the twin boundaries effects on the domain walls motion. Since a linear correlation between macroscopic volume initial susceptibility and multiparallel-twinned grains volume fractions was found, the magnetic contribution of multiparallel-twinned grains was separated from that of the others (single crystal grains, or in other way twinned grains) by means of the mixing rule.

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Figures

Fig. 1 SEM images of the starting nano-powders a) Co_3O_4 and b) $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$. (2- column)

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of the starting oxides reacted at 700 °C, 800 °C and 850 °C, before milling. In the inset the (3 1 1) peak at half height is enlarged for the three samples (1.5- column)

Fig. 3 Comparison of Sedigraph analyses of the as-calcined and milled powders. (1.5- column)

Fig. 4 XRD patterns of the reacted powders after planetary milling. Cobalt ferrite peaks are labeled with the respective Miller indices. In the inset the (3 1 1) peak at half height is enlarged for the three samples (1.5- column)

Fig. 5 SEM morphology of the milled powders calcined at a) 850 °C and b) 1000 °C. (2- column)

Fig. 6 Influence of milling time on the mean particle size distribution (PSD). Labels refer to the diameter of milling media. (1.5- column)

Fig. 7 Density of the cold-consolidated and sintered samples as a function of the mean particle size (D_{50}) of the starting powders. (single column)

Fig. 8 SEM morphology of the as-sintered surfaces: (a,b) CFO 800 °C; (c,d) CFO 850 °C and (e, f) CFO 1000 °C. (2- column)

Fig. 9 SEM morphology of twin lamellae (sample CFO 850 °C). (single column)

Fig. 10 SEM morphology of the fracture surface of the CFO sample sintered at 1000 °C. (1.5 column)

Fig. 11 Induced magnetization of the sintered samples vs. magnetic field strength. Magnetic field strength increases as a result of the samples being brought closer to the permanent magnet at five set distances. The solid lines follow the Rayleigh law parameterized by initial susceptibility (χ_i), and Rayleigh coefficient (α) [26]. (single column)

Fig. 12 Plot of volume magnetic susceptibility ($\chi = \chi_i + \alpha H$) as a function of magnetic field strength (H), and multiparallel-twinned grains volume fraction (G_{MPT}). (1.5 column)

Tables

Tab. 1 Particle sizes weighted on equivalent spherical diameter (d_{nl}) and on volume (d_{nv}) after milling of the CFO powders calcined at 800 °C, 850°C and 1000°C.